

Evaluation of Classroom Observations in College Teaching: The Versatility of the Lecture Method

Sol G. Simbulan, Ph.D.

School of Education, San Isidro College, Malaybalay City, Bukidnon, 8700

✉ ssimbultan@sic.edu.ph

How to cite this paper:

Simbulan, S. (2023). Evaluation of Classroom Observations in College Teaching: The Versatility of the Lecture Method. *School of Education Research Journal*, 3(1): 76-93.

Received: February 28, 2023

Accepted: February 28, 2023

Published: March 5, 2023

Copyright © 2022 by authors and School of Education Research Journal.

This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International License (CC BY 4.0).

<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

ABSTRACT

Highlighted in this paper is the result of class observations of the School of Education (SED) instructors during the first semester for the academic year 2022-2023. Eight full-time and part time SED instructors' classes were observed and their performance was rated to be *excellent* in the criteria set in the instrument. Generally, the opening prayer served as their preliminary activity together with the checking of attendance and establishing of rapport between the instructors and the students. The lecture method in combination with other teaching strategies like discussion, demonstration, use of PPT, video clips, exercises and activities were utilized by the teachers to keep the students engaged in the lesson. Class participation was evident. Assessment was rated as *very good*. On the whole, the college instructors successfully scaffold their lesson for the day capturing the relevance of the teaching strategies in their delivery of instruction.

Subject Area

Teaching

Keywords: *Classroom Observation, Lecture Method*

INTRODUCTION

Classroom observation is a powerful tool to enable students and teachers in developing an analysis of teaching and learning experiences, strategies, assessment, class interaction and engagement. Classroom observations provide teachers with constructive feedback to reflect upon their classroom management and instructional strategies (Puri, 2021). The fundamental purpose is to improve student performance by improving the instructional delivery/teaching strategies of the teachers.

During the academic year 2022-2023 the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) gave San Isidro College the go-signal to have a full-swing face-to-face classes in all levels. As a perfunctory

practice for all schools' instructors are observed in their classes. The criteria for evaluation constitute *Learning outcomes, instructional content and delivery, Instructor's presence and support; Learning experience and interaction; and assessment.*

Under the criteria on *learning outcomes* the instructors are observed on whether the Intended Learning Outcome (ILO) are clearly stated and are aligned with the Course Learning Outcome (CLO); and whether the structure and plan of the day's class and the expected output/expected outcome/s is/are clearly stated.

In the criteria on *Instructional content and delivery* the instructor is evaluated on the following indicators: The instructional materials (content) represent up-to-date theory and practice in the discipline, and contribute to the attainment of the ILO; The instructional materials are presented in a variety of ways (lecture, text readings, video, etc.) in order to engage the students and encourage them to connect to the content; and that the Learning Management System (LMS) or technology's features were optimized for effective teaching-learning process.

In the criteria on *Instructor's presence and support* the indicators include: the instructor's support is manifested in giving feedback, rejoinders, comments, response to queries, suggestions and clarifying questions and in providing scaffold directions for the activities; and the instructor's presence is felt by guiding the students to attain the intended learning outcomes through encouraging and monitoring them to perform and move or progress towards the attainment of the intended learning outcomes until the end of the class.

Under the criteria on *Learning experience and interaction*, the indicators are: The learning experiences offered to students are relevant and promote the attainment of the ILO; the learning experiences are varied and promote high student engagement or participation; and the learning activities and tasks provide opportunities for peer interaction and self-directed learning.

In the criteria on *assessment*, the indicators include: the assessments are clearly aligned to the ILO and seek evidence to assess the attainment of the ILO; specific descriptive criteria (such as a rubrics) are provided so the students are guided in achieving the intended outcomes of the assessments which is also use by the instructor in evaluating the students' outcomes/outputs or performance; and students are provided with multiple opportunities to receive feedback at appropriate times to track learning.

The rationale of this paper is to serve as a document on class observations conducted in the SED as part of keeping a record on the essential aspects of what are included in a lesson presentation. It also serves as a vehicle of enriching and strengthening the different parts of the lesson presentation and viewing the significance of the teaching strategies and lesson delivery to improve student engagement in the lessons.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The analysis on the classroom observations of the SED faculty during the first semester of the academic year 2022-2023 specifically focused on the following questions:

1. What is the evaluation of the SED instructors' performance in their classroom observations considering the criteria on learning outcomes; instructional content and delivery; Instructor's presence and support; learning experience and interaction; and assessment?

2. What are the actual observation results in the following parts of the lesson:
 - 2.1 preliminary activities;
 - 2.2 teaching delivery/strategies used;
 - 2.3 student engagements;
 - 2.4 assessment; and
 - 2.5 closing of the lesson?

METHODOLOGY

Classroom observations were done during the first semester of the academic year 2022-2023 to eight full-time and part time college instructors of San Isidro College from November 15 to December 1, 2022. The class observation instrument developed by the College was used as the tool for evaluation. There were 5 criteria for evaluation with a total of 13 statement indicators.

San Isidro College is the only Catholic Higher Education institution in Malaybalay City. It offers the degree programs for the School of Arts and Sciences (SAS), School of Nursing (SON), School of Midwifery (SOM), School of Accountancy (SOA), School of Business Administration (SBA) & Office Administration, School of Engineering (SOE), School of Information Technology (SIT), and the School of Education (SED). The college population is less than a thousand with the SED population of almost two hundred students. During the first semester the School of Education has 8 full time faculty and 11 part time faculty. There were 8 instructors both from the full time and part time who were observed in their actual face-to-face classes.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

SED instructors' performance during their class observations

Table 1 shows the consolidated report on the ratings given to the 8 SED faculty observed during the first semester of the academic year 2022-2023. Table 2 reflects the summary of ratings in the criteria.

Table 1.*Results of teacher's performance on class observations*

Criteria for class observations	Mean	QD
A. Learning Outcomes	4.62	Excellent
1. The Intended Learning Outcomes (ILO) are clearly stated and are aligned with the Course Learning Outcomes (CLO).		
2. The structure and plan of the day's class and the expected output/expected outcome is/are clearly stated.	4.75	Excellent
B. Instructional Content and Delivery	4.50	Excellent
3. The instructional materials (content) represent up-to-date theory and practice in the discipline, and contribute to the attainment of the ILO		
4. The instructional materials are presented in a variety of ways (lecture, text readings, video, etc.) in order to engage the students and encourage them to connect to the content	4.50	Excellent
5. The Learning Management System or technology's features were optimized for effective teaching-learning process.	4.62	Excellent
C. Instructor's Presence and Support	4.62	Excellent
6. The instructor's support is manifested in giving feedback, rejoinders, comments, response to queries, suggestions and clarificatory questions and in providing scaffolded directions for the activities.		
7. The instructor's presence is felt by guiding the students to attain the ILO through encouraging and monitoring them to perform and move or progress towards the attainment of the intended learning outcomes until the end of the class.	4.50	Excellent
D. Learning Experience and Interaction	4.75	Excellent
8. The learning experiences offered to students are relevant and promote the attainment of the Intended Learning Outcomes.		
9. The learning experiences are varied and promote high student engagement or participation.	4.38	Excellent
10. The learning activities and tasks provide opportunities for peer interaction and self-directed learning.	4.12	Very Good
E. Assessment	4.00	Very Good
11. The assessments are clearly aligned to the Intended Learning Outcomes and seek evidence to assess the attainment of the ILO.		
12. Specific descriptive criteria (such as a rubrics) are provided so the students are guided in achieving the intended outcomes of the assessments which is also use by the instructor in evaluating the students' outcomes/outputs or performance.	3.88	Very Good
13. Students are provided with multiple opportunities to receive feedback at appropriate times to track learning.	3.88	Very Good
Overall	4.39	Excellent

Table 2.*Summary of the observation results in the different criteria*

Criteria for class observation	Mean	Rank	QD
Learning outcomes	4.68	1	Excellent
Instructional content and delivery	4.54	3	Excellent
Instructor's presence and support	4.56	2	Excellent
Learning experience and interaction	4.42	4	Excellent
Assessment	3.92	5	Very Good

Evaluation of Classroom Observations in College Teaching: The Versatility of the Lecture Method

Table 1 shows the overall ratings of the SED instructors with a mean of 4.39 indicating that their teaching performance is *excellent*. The criteria on *Learning outcomes, instructional content and delivery, Instructor's presence and support*; and *Learning experience and interaction* showed that the SED faculty were excellent in these areas. It is on the criteria in *assessment* where their rating is *very good*.

In Table 2 the criteria on *intended learning outcomes* ranked first, implying that the instructors wanted the students to be aware of the objectives of the lesson. In many ways, this is essential so that the students will have some directions in what they are to expect from their class lesson. The *instructors' presence and support* come second in rank. The instructor's support is manifested in giving feedback, rejoinders, comments, response to queries, suggestions and clarifying questions and in providing scaffold directions for the activities. The instructor's presence is felt by guiding the students to attain the ILO through encouraging and monitoring them to perform and move or progress towards the attainment of the intended learning outcomes until the end of the class. The *delivery of instruction and teaching strategies* ranked third. Here, the instructors used a variety of lesson presentations to engage the students. Fourth in rank is on *learning experience and interaction*. Student's engagement and participation are also given importance in the conduct of the lesson to check on whether they have understood the topic.

Last in rank is on *assessment*. In analyzing the statements in the indicators, one could observe that it is not easy to evaluate whether the assessments given are clearly aligned to the Intended Learning outcomes and whether these seek evidence to assess the attainment of the ILO. It is also noted that not all teachers assess their teaching using specific descriptive criteria/rubrics. It is further noted that the indicator "provided with multiple opportunities to receive feedback to track their learning" could not be always attained during class duration. Feedback is usually given by teachers but considering the qualifier "multiple feedback" in the indicators would seem too challenging to achieve. As observed, it is during the discussion on questioning where instructors usually gave their feedback on students' responses. This practice is visually observed. The feedback from formative assessments like quizzes and activities are usually in quantitative ratings, and some use rubrics to rate these.

Observation results on the parts of the lesson

Matrices 1 to 6 reflect the results on observations done in the different parts of the lesson starting from the preliminaries to the closing of the lessons and the comments on the general observations of the instructors.

Matrix 1.

Observations on teacher's performance on Preliminary activities prior to the Lesson Proper

T-1	Prayers were recited by the class. Teacher checks attendance.
T-2	Teacher is prompt in her class. A student leads the prayer.
T-3	Prayer was led by the student. Attendance was checked. Teacher prepares the students for the class
T-4	Teacher checks attendance and many were absent making her wonder why. Some informed her about the activities of those who were not around. Prayer was said in Filipino by the student
T-5	Prayers were said. Attendance was checked. Teacher gave instructions on schedules and protocols in a matter-of-fact manner.

T-6	Teacher is prompt in her class and the students are well-behaved. A student leads the prayer and proper greetings to the teacher and classmates were done.
T-7	Prayers were recited by the class. Teacher checks attendance and if they wear their NSTP uniform
T-8	Teacher is prompt in his class. Students were mostly boys with only one girl. A student leads the prayer

Generally, it is observed that prayers were recited before classes start. This is expected considering that San Isidro College is a Catholic institution of learning. While there is no rule or prescriptions from the administration that prayers have to be said before any activity, this practice seems to be the insignia of religious schools. San Isidro College bears the banner as the only Catholic higher education institution in Malaybalay City and as such it lives up to its being one through religious formation. One value embedded in prayer is on praise and thanksgiving for the Almighty to begin the lesson. Implicitly, the value formation is instilled in the mind of the students that they carry in their lives and maybe in the future when they become teachers, as well.

It is observed that teachers prepare the class by checking students' attendance and providing them a welcoming atmosphere. In a class where there are very limited number of students, it is very obvious that teachers and students have a good rapport. Teachers really follow-up their students and are very concern as to their whereabouts.

Matrix 2.

Observations on teacher's performance on Teaching delivery/strategies used

T-1	<p>Teaching Strategy- Lecture Discussion integrating ICT/PPT</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher reviews the previous lesson specifically on the laboratory activity e.g., 2 jars of water and baking soda experiment, etc. She asks the students their observations of the experiments. Teacher utilizes the PPT presentation showing illustration e.g., greenhouse gases and asks "what happens if there are greenhouse gases?" Students were asks to give their responses. Teacher asks questions while doing the lecture and calls students to respond. Teacher uses practical examples that the students could relate in their day-to-day experience. Teacher asks the students to go to their groups for the activity. The Performance task: "<i>Trace the greenhouse gases...</i>". Teacher shows the example on what the students are to do. She verifies if the students understood the instructions for the activity. The activity questions were flashed on the computer screen. These guide the students on what to do. After 15 minutes the students were asked to go back to their seats and the group presentation was done by the students The Lecture method integrating ICT/PPT presentation was evidently utilized by the teacher.
T-2	<p>Teaching Strategy- Lecture-Discussion-activity</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> A brief reminder on the topic last meeting was mentioned before the teacher introduces the topic for the day which is on LOGIC Teacher presents the objectives through the PPT. Teacher has the students seated in their group to make them ready for the activity, she presented the work to be done and set a timer for the activity. This is to identify if the statement is True or False or sometimes True or false. This serves as a quiz for the student which synergizes them

Evaluation of Classroom Observations in College Teaching: The Versatility of the Lecture Method

- Teacher used this sentence as a prelude to her lesson: *What is statement?* The topic is on Logic statements and Quantifiers
 - Teacher gives a lecture on the proponents: Leibniz and George Boole. The Logic statements like: question, command, opinion, fact was given examples and the students are to identify the statements as presented in the PPT
 - Teacher gives Seatwork #1 where they have to identify if the phrase is a *statement* or *not a statement*. Students cooperatively work in groups.
 - Then the topic on *Logic connectives and symbols* was presented and the *truth value table* were presented. Students were given examples and they also answered the activity given
 - The teacher actively engaged the students in every activity so that there is no dull moment with them.
 - The Lecture Method was vibrantly demonstrated by the teacher facilitated through PPT, activities on the board and seat work.
-

T-3 Teaching Strategy- Lecture and demonstration (carousel style)

Part I- Lecture

- Teacher reviews the lesson. The students were asked to discuss what they had done with their assignment on the “meal plan”
- The teacher is alive in questioning the students and the students generally responded in visayan.
- The teacher utilizes the PPT presentation although he did not use the projector hence the students at the back could not view what is presented.
- The teacher presents the objectives for the lesson of the day – (on aerobics)
- He stands and delivers the lecture moving about to give all the students the chance of viewing how he delivers using his body language.
- The lecture includes the importance of exercise and the types of exercise
- After the lecture, he asks the students to get ½ CW for his assessment.
- The teacher asks the students to move outside to the gym for the actual field demonstration on physical activities
- The Lecture Method with PPT presentation served as the strategy of the teacher prior to the field demo outside the classroom.

Part II- Field Demonstration

- Teacher already prepares the gym and the instructions are placed in in the different areas (circular position).
 - The activity he labeled as Tabatha Circuit. There are listed steps for the group of students to perform. The music was also prepared in such a way that after each activity, the students perform while the music is playing. When it stops, they move to the next area just like in a carousel strategy
 - The students perform as expected and teachers checks on everyone if they did the moves correctly
 - Actual body movements were exhibited by the students and the carousel strategy was employed.
-

T-4 Teaching Strategy- Lecture Discussion

- *Review of previous lesson-*
 - Teacher asks the students on what they have discussed last week. She asks what they have learned.
 - Teacher continues the discussion of the topic on “*diskurso*” and reminds the students on their assignment on “*uri ng diskurso*”
 - *Presentation of the lesson-*
-

- Teacher lectures on the topic on “*pagsusulat*”. Teacher is confident and is articulate in giving her lecture. The objectives of the lesson were not articulated because the teacher continues the lesson from her asking the students the question on their previous lesson,
- Teacher groups the students to do any of the forms of what they have written in their assignment. They choose what “*sulatin*” they will write. They will do this activity the whole remaining duration of their time because they will continue the activity next meeting
- The questioning done by the teacher were mostly lower-order although there were instances when higher-order questions were raised.
- While the students are doing the activity the teacher wrote on the board the following:
Pamantayan sa pagsusulat:

• <i>Nilalaman</i>	30%
• <i>Pagtatanaw ng mga detalye</i>	25%
• <i>Kahusay pagsulat</i>	<u>25%</u>
	80%
- The Lecture Method with some questionings in the lecture was exhibited by the teacher.

T-5 Teaching Strategy- Lecture and demonstration

Part I- Lecture

- Teacher lectures while sitting down, but she can capture the students’ attention because of her voice and her hand actions. The way she gives a lecture is like a “mother to a child” giving instructions and directions at the same time weaving a story to elucidate her examples and giving advises to them particularly in grooming, health, personality, etc.
- She “code-switches” in her presentation of the lecture with examples clearly articulated in Visayas as though she was an adviser as to how students show behave, perform, and exude themselves.
- The examples given are often practical and relatable to the students, sometimes calling on individual students to illustrate the example.
- Teacher integrates the core values of SIC but also injects her own perceptions/opinions on what students should do in the future e.g., “*do not marry yet. Work after you graduate.2 years in the Philippines, after these service work abroad to earn more and help your parents, buy a house, buy a car, etc....enjoy life while young....*”
- Some examples and advises were practical and down-to-earth telling the students the consequences of their actions, e.g., what will happen if the students do not obey... do the opposite on what they are taught or told to do....
- After the lecture, the teacher asks the students to move outside to the gym for the actual field demonstration on physical activities
- The Lecture teaching strategy where most of the talking and discussion was done by the teacher.

Part II- Field Demonstration

- Teacher gives instructions for students to demonstrate. She demonstrates the particular moves and the students follow
 - The teacher shows enthusiasm in the actual performance, exhibiting the moves actively and effectively
 - The students perform as expected and teachers checks on everyone if they did the moves correctly
-

- Actual field performance was done by the students through the instruction of the teacher.
-

T-6 Teaching Strategy- Eclectic/Varied Strategies – Lecture using PPT, Video Clip, Cooperative Group Learning, Discussion

- Teacher lets the students sit in a circular position to review on the previous lesson. She prepared a box where questions written in a slip of paper are rolled for the students to answer. A music was played such that when the music stops, the student holding the box will pick one question to answer this. After the student responded and the teacher approving of the answer, the music is played again and the box is passed around. This goes on until all the questions were uncovered.
 - The questions raised were mostly HOTS e.g. *What are the types of relationships, Explain the theory of love, explain why transparency is important, Why is there a need for internal relationship, What do you mean by interpersonal relations, why interpersonal relation is important.*
 - Teacher presents the new topic on *Theories of Interpersonal relationships*. She presents the objectives through PPT.
 - Teacher raises the question: *In what ways can interpersonal relationship enduring or brief?* The theory on *uncertainty reduction theory* was presented. A video clip was shown by the teacher, after which she raises HOT questions for students to answer/discuss.
 - Teacher gives an activity for the students to perform. She gives them 15 minutes to work on the activity. Each student has to work on one activity question.
 - The next theory –*social exchange theory* - was presented through a video. Again, the teacher raises a HOTS question. Two groups were formed for the next activity where they will write their responses in a sheet of manila paper. The column on: *Theory- Cost- Benefit* were asked. While the students worked on the activity, the teacher moved about to check on their responses.
 - Teacher exhibited the versatility of the lecture method by integrating other strategies in the presentation. There was no dull moment during the presentation and time management was observed.
-

T-7 Teaching Strategy- Lecture Demonstration

- Teacher lectures on: The characteristics of a good first-aider; how to check on the CABG; when the best time to give a CPR is. Fluency of communication is evident in the lecture. The objectives were not stated specifically as the teacher seems to embed this in her discussion.
 - Teacher demonstrates step-by-step on how to do the CPR using the pillow as its IMs.
 - Teacher asks questions whether the students understood the lecture-demonstration on how to do the CPR
 - Teacher asks the students to do a return-demonstration. She asks for volunteers, then later assign them by pairs and rates their performance, if they followed the step-by-step process
 - The lecture method was used to demonstrate the activity. Instructions were given by the teacher for the students to make a return-demo on what she lectured.
-

T-8 Teaching Strategy- Lecture using PPT & student's discussion based from their responses in the personality Assessment that they took

- Teacher asks the students to recap what they have learned last meeting on the different intelligences.
 - In opening the next topic, the teacher asks the students whether they have taken the 16 personality tests.
 - Teacher presents the new topic on *Types of Personality*. He presents the objectives through PPT.
-

-
- Teacher presents each personality type, giving its characteristics, the advantages and disadvantages through PPT presentations.
 - After the lecture and discussion, he asks who among the students represent this type of personality and ask them to explain why.
 - This type of discussion follows the same pattern where teacher presents the type of personality, gives the characteristics, advantages, and disadvantages; then asks the students as to who has this personality type and explain why.
 - The lecture method was enthusiastically exhibited by the teacher making use of the PPT and questioning techniques.
-

Research on the effectiveness of teaching strategies on students' academic performance reveals that the most effective teaching strategy is the teacher-student interactive teaching method seconded by student-centered teaching strategies (Pao, 2022). There are several reasons why teaching strategies are important in affecting learning. One reason is that different students learn in different ways and a variety of teaching strategies can reach students who learn differently. Additionally, effective teaching strategies can engage students in the material and make learning more enjoyable.

It is observed that the dominant teaching strategy is the lecture method spiced with other strategies to enhance the presentation. The lecture method is the most versatile teaching strategy especially in the tertiary level where communication and instruction are very essential. It is further observed that teachers dominantly did the talking while the students' pay attention and perform the tasks instructed to them. Lectures allow instructors to use the best teaching methods possible by covering a lot of grounds for their lessons to be clearly understood (Go Greenva, 2022). It is the strategy that could cover a lot of topics within a period of time. Its versatility is very well showcased by the college teachers. Effective teachers enhance their teaching prowess through strategies that best accommodate the learning needs of the students. And, the lecture method seems to be the answer.

The lecture method of teaching is the most popular and commonly used. The main objective of teaching is to make students understand the learning concepts and prepare them for the real world. Therefore, teachers have been incorporating different strategies to enhance the efficacy of the lecture methods. In addition to the lecture method, teachers are integrating other methods to effectively teach students and make students active participants in the learning process. In order to make the lectures more engaging and captivating, teachers use different strategies. These strategies enhance the outcomes of the lecture method and improve the learning retention rate of the students (Teachmint, 2022).

As observed most teachers utilized the PPT presentation as this could very well facilitate their lecture. Activities are also prepared by the teacher to keep the students engaged in the lesson. Teaching and *learning by doing* keep the lesson alive and this could activate the senses of the learners. Skills needed by the teacher in a lecture method include communication skills, creative skills, time management skills, and class management skills. The teacher needs to have the strategies in ensuring learner engagement, in incorporating audio-visual aids, and in planning the lesson when using the lecture method.

Matrix 3.

Observations on students' engagement during the lesson

T-1	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform their group tasks cooperatively.• A student for every group presents their report showing their illustrations. As observed the students mostly speak in Visayas or they code-switch from English to Visayan.• The activity enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion. Cooperative group work activity was also present. Students give their learning and they're being a part in contributing the to global warming, with the implication/insights on how they could help the environment
T-2	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform their group tasks cooperatively• The activity enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion. Cooperative group work activity was evident.
T-3	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform the tasks asked by the teacher.• The lecture enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion• The demonstration is well participated by the students. They performed the different moves as specified in the areas.
T-4	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students worked in groups as instructed by the teacher.• Students reported on what they have done in their work
T-5	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform the tasks asked by the teacher.• The students enjoyed the activity as they could relate to the examples presented.• The lecture enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion.• The demonstration is well participated by the students. They performed the different moves demonstrated by the teacher.
T-6	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform their group tasks cooperatively.• A student for every group presents their report showing their responses on the 2 theories their cost and their benefits. As observed the students were open in their communication, speaking in English most of the time although there were instances when they code-switch from English to Visayan.• The activity enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion. Cooperative group work activity was evident.
T-7	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students demonstrate through actual performance on how to do the CPR• All students were called on to participate because they were assigned in pairs and the teacher rates their Performance
T-8	<i>Student Engagement</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none">• Students perform the tasks asked by the teacher.• The students enjoyed the activity as they could relate to the personality type presented.• The activity enhances the students to actively participate in the class discussion.

Based from the observation, teachers keep the students engaged in their lesson through the activities that they prepared. There were several activities either done individually or in groups.

Most of the activities were done in groups to allow more participation and cooperation from the students. They become more competitive as they do the activities. Vicky Trowler (2010) talks of student engagement as enhanced by active participation both inside and outside the classroom; in collaborative activity of the students; and in the assessment of their learning. Encouraging student engagement in this contemporary educational landscape would include a combination of traditional modes like the lecture alongside with more participatory and experiential learning activities such as role plays, simulations, inquiry and problem-based learning, pictures and drawings, research projects, video clips and others (Healey and Jenkins, 2009).

Students' class participation in classroom may range from passive to active participations. They may just sit quietly, taking notes, listening, doing something else, or asking questions, giving opinions, or answering questions posed (Mohd Yusof, et al 2011; Hussein, 2010; Bas, 2010). The first four is a passive type of participation while the latter is an active type of classroom engagement.

Dynamic learners engage actively by playing the roles of information seekers. They ask questions, give opinions or simply answer questions posed by the instructor or fellow students. According to Davis (2009), student's enthusiasm and willingness to participate in a classroom through these verbal engagements will create a conducive classroom environment.

Matrix 4.

Observations on Assessment used/given

T-1	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The insights that the students give could assess their learning about the topic. Teacher gives the assignment for next meeting
T-2	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The activity that the students perform indicates their learning from the topics presented. Teacher gives the assignment for next meeting
T-3	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the lecture activity the teacher gave them a short quiz in a ½ CW sheet of paper. Questions given: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> How can aerobic exercise benefit one's health? Describe 3 advantages. Is it preferable to exercise once a day? Explain your response. In the Demo activity the teacher checks on the group to do the moves/steps that that were listed.
T-4	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher gives a quiz in a ¼ sheet of paper, dictating the question to them.
T-5	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> In the lecture activity the teacher told the class to study on the lecture she gave In the Demo activity the teacher checks on individual student to do the move that she dictates if they could follow
T-6	<i>Assessment</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The activity that the students perform indicates their learning from the topics presented. Teacher gives the assignment for next meeting

Evaluation of Classroom Observations in College Teaching: The Versatility of the Lecture Method

T-7 *Assessment*

- After all the students have demonstrated, the teacher gave her observations and feedback: e.g., students did not sanitize; did not call 911; ladies did not fix /hide their hair; the CABC was not followed strictly
 - Teacher asks “What lesson did the student learn?”
-

T-8 *Assessment*

- The activity that the students perform indicates their learning from the topics presented.
 - Teacher gives the assignment for next meeting
-

Assessment is an integral part of instruction, as it determines whether or not the goals of education are met. Classroom assessment affects teacher’s performance, students’ performance, achieving of ILO, accomplishing the lessons and activities for the topic; class management, and others. It inspires teachers to ask whether they are teaching what they think they are teaching; whether the students are learning was they think they should be learning (edutopia, 2008).

As observed, some teachers provided assessment where each student answer the quiz given at the end of the lesson. Some assessment done by the teachers simply asked them to respond as to what they have learned from the lesson that day. Actual demonstration was also used to assess the students’ learning, while the teacher graded their performance.

In some cases when the activities are rich and varied, the activities themselves serves as the assessment and rubric guides are employed by the teacher. The reporting from the groups became the basis for grading students’ performance, and the teacher makes the rating scale for grading them. Gibbs (2003) states that assessment has six main functions, namely: capturing student’s time and attention; generating appropriate student learning activity; providing timely feedback which students pay attention to; helping students to internalize the disciplines standards and notion of equality; generating marks or grades which distinguish between students or enable pass/fail decisions to be made; and providing evidence for others outside the course to enable them to judge the appropriateness of standards on the course.

Matrix 5.

Observations on Closing the lesson/class session

T-1 *Closing*

- As a whole the teacher was able to successfully scaffold the lesson smoothly before she dismisses the class, reminding them to check on their google class for updates.
-

T-2 *Closing*

- The teacher successfully ended the lesson smoothly as the students are also very responsive and well-engaged in the discussion.
 - The teacher closes the lesson meaningfully and tell them to study on their assignment for next meeting.
-

T-3 *Closing*

- As a whole the teacher successfully delivered the lesson and the students were very responsive and well-engaged in the discussion and actual field performance.
-

T-4	<i>Closing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> There was no meaningful closing of the class. Teacher dismissed the class and gave them their assignment
T-5	<i>Closing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> As a whole the teacher successfully delivered her lesson and the students are also very responsive and well-engaged in the discussion and actual field performance.
T-6	<i>Closing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher successfully scaffolds the lesson smoothly as the students are also very responsive and well-engaged in the discussion. The teacher closes the lesson meaningfully. The students had their closing prayers and bid farewell to each other and their teachers politely.
T-7	<i>Closing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Teacher wraps up the lecture and closes the class with a prayer. She told the class that she will repeat the assessment on the actual demonstration of the CPR for them to master the process.
T-8	<i>Closing</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher successfully delivered the lesson smoothly as the students are also very responsive and well-engaged in the discussion. The teacher closes the lesson asking the students to view their assignment in the google class.

The closing of the day's lesson is one essential part of instruction. The way a lesson ends affects a learner's ability to organize, evaluate and store the information. Closure is the step where the teacher wraps up a lesson plan and help students organize the information in a meaningful context in their minds. This helps students better understand what they have learned and provides a way in which they can apply it to the world around them.

A strong closure can help students better retain information beyond the immediate learning environment. A brief summary or overview is often appropriate. This does not have to be an extensive review. A helpful activity when closing a lesson is to engage students in a quick discussion about what they learned and what it means to them (Lewis, 2019).

Matrix 6.

Summary on Observed Comments

T-1	COMMENTS:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> The teacher is energetic and enthusiastic in her teaching. She is well prepared with her lesson and she kept her students active and engaged in the activities that she prepared. The teacher presented her lesson clearly with the integration of ICT/PPT which is good because the students are more of visual learners and to keep abreast with recent trends in teaching. The teacher used practical examples in her presentation and this is good so that the students could easily relate and understand the topic. There is a student who came late for class. The scaffolding of the lesson was done smoothly.
-----	-----------	--

T-2 COMMENTS:

- The teacher shows vitality in her teaching such that the students are active and well-facilitated as well.
 - Activities were presented every topic & subtopics keeping the students well-engaged.
 - Teacher's voice is loud enough for students to pay attention and understand the lecture.
 - Values integration was not explicitly stated although the very act of good teaching is a value in itself.
 - The scaffolding of the lesson from the start to finish was done well.
-

T-3 COMMENTS

- The teacher exudes confidence in teaching. He showed a well disposition and pleasant personality trying his best to deliver his lecture in English.
 - He explains the topic clearly and slowly with his PPT presentation, although he was not able to project these well in the DLP.
 - Both lecture and demonstration were delivered very smoothly.
-

T-4 COMMENTS:

- The teacher is particular on student's attendance although at this observation more than half of the class were not present.
- The teacher exhibits confidence in her teaching and is articulate in her lecture.
- Values integration was not verbally articulated although implicitly the teacher wants to let the students develop good work values particularly on attendance.
- On the Criteria for writing [*Pamantayan sa Pagsulat*] It seems that the percentage given did not reach 100% and this would seem unfair for the students in this particular aspect.

Why is the total percentage only 80%? Where is the 20%? This would appear to be like a rubric and generally, this should have a total of 100%. This is because, if the teacher will not give the score of 80% to the student/s which is a perfect score in this rubric, the score of the students will fall below 80% or even a failing mark.

- As a whole the class was successfully delivered.
-

T-5 COMMENTS

- The teacher employed the old style of lecturing where she merely sits and talks to explain the topic.
 - She delivers her lecture with enthusiasm code-switching from English to Visayan to make the students understand.
 - The students seem to be happy and at ease with the aura of the teacher.
 - The class ends very smoothly and the students seems to be well engaged.
-

T-6 COMMENTS

- The teacher exudes good aura to her class, following the smooth transition of the lesson from the opening of class to the closing portion.
 - The lesson was well prepared and the activities were well presented, keeping the students actively engaged in the class.
 - Several strategies were employed by the teacher making the students active in the process. Values integration is evidently shown in the preparation of the teacher. Every moment was fully utilized. Good class management was very evident.
 - There is evidence that the students are intently listening to their teachers as they are well-managed.
 - The class ends very smoothly and the students are well engaged.
-

T-7 COMMENTS:

- The teacher exudes confidence in her teaching. Demonstrating the CPR in a step-by-step process was done while students watched how the process was done.
- Asking the students to perform the CPR is good because the teacher can see whether the students understood the topic or whether they were attentive/observant in the demo.
- Giving feedback after all the students had performed the return-demo was good so that the students can rectify their error. Maybe next meeting, they could again be tested if they could perfectly do the CPR based from teacher's feedback on their flaws.
- Teacher gave feedback on the demonstration of the students after all have performed the demo. She also used this as her assessment.
- Since the teacher finds flaws in the demo of the students, she told them that they will perform the same activity next meeting for mastery as this is very important for them to learn, so they can save lives.
- As a whole, the lesson was successfully done.

T-8 COMMENTS

- The teacher "stands and delivers" his class lecture exuding enthusiasm in his presentation.
- He lectures in full view and is articulate in his presentation delivering his lecture with vibrancy, sometimes code-switching from English to Visayan to make the students understand.
- The topic on personality types was very interesting to the students keeping them actively engaged in the class. After describing the personality type, the characteristics, advantage and disadvantage, he asks the students who belong to this type of personality based from their own assessment on their personality test.
- The class ends very smoothly and the students seems to be well engaged.
- The teacher reminds students to be kept posted in their assignments and lectures in the google class.

In general, the eight instructors have demonstrated their best teaching practices, employed the lecture method and integrated other strategies to enhance students' participation and engagement in the class. They have smoothly scaffolded their lesson and activities starting from the *preliminaries* to the *closing* of the lesson, embedding the different aspects that could facilitate their teaching, e.g., opening of the lesson, presentation of objectives, the art of questioning, the integration of higher-order-thinking skills, the use of PPT and other technologies, motivation, seat work /group activities, assessment, time management, fluency of communication, time management, and closing of the lesson.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Class observation has a pivotal role in the continuing professional training, development, and assessment of teachers. There are general and common strategies that can be effective in teaching which include using a variety of methods to engage students. The lecture method can be made interactive by involving students as active participants. This could encourage students to stay immersed in the class, improving retention and giving long lasting impact on the students. Teachers have to be clear and concise in their instructions, providing adequate practice opportunities, enriching instructional materials and visual aids like videos, images, graphs that

enrich the imaginative power of the students and offering feedback that is both positive and constructive.

Additionally, it is important to be flexible and adapt teaching methods that best meet the needs of the students. Since lecturing is inevitable in classroom learning, teachers need a solid plan to facilitate and improve the quality of the lecturing process. Communication skills, creative skills, time management skills, and class management skills are essential for teachers to facilitate and improve effective teaching strategies, like lecturing in the classroom.

REFERENCE

- Abdullah, M.Y., Mahbod, M.H., Abu B., and Noor R. (2012). Students Participation in classroom: What motivates them to speak? *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, **51**:516-522 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2012.08.199>
- Bas, G. (2010). Effects of multiple intelligences instruction strategy on students' achievement levels and attitudes towards english lesson. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, **5**(3).
- Davis, B. G. (2009). *Tools for teaching* (2nd.ed.). San Francisco: Jossey-Bass.
- Gibbs (2003). *The Importance of Assessment in The Teaching Learning Process*. www.ipl.org/essay/The-Importance-Of-Assessment-In-The-Teaching-PK8C6S36CE8R
- Go Greenva (2022). *Teachers' Methods of Teaching Have a Great Impact on Students' Academic Performance*. <https://www.gogreenva.org/how-teaching-strategies-can-affect-student-learning/>
- Edutopia (2008). *Why is assessment important?* <https://www.edutopia.org/assessment>
- Healey, M. & Jenkins, A. (2009). *Developing undergraduate research and inquiry*. York: Higher Education Academy. <https://www.heacademy.ac.uk/node/3146>
- Hussein, G. (2010). The Attitudes of Undergraduate Students towards Motivation and Technology in a Foreign Language Classroom. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, **2**(2) 14-24.
- Lewis, Beth (2019). *Writing a Lesson Plan: Closure and Context*. www.thoughtco.com/lesson-plan-step-5-closure-2081851
- O'Leary, Matt (2013). *Classroom Observation - A guide to the effective observation of teaching and learning*. <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.34417.07523>
- Mohd Yusof, et al. (2011). *The Dynamics of Student Participation in Classroom: Observation on level and forms of participation*. Paper presented at Learning and Teaching Congress of UKM, 18th-20th. December, Penang, Malaysia.
- Puri, Dimple (2021). *Classroom Observations: The Power of Reflection*. Connected TOT
- Pao, Karen (2022). *Top 8 Best Points on the Importance of Teaching Strategies in the Classroom*. <https://teachersarethebest.com/importance-of-teaching-strategies/#>
- Healey, M. and Jenkins, A. (2009) *Developing undergraduate research and inquiry*. York: Higher Education Academy. <https://www.heacademy.ac.uk/node/3146>
- Hébert, A. and Hauf, P. (2015) 'Student learning through service learning: Effects on academic development, civic responsibility, interpersonal skills and practical skills. *Active Learning in Higher Education*, **16**(1), 37-49.
- Jensen, K. and Bagnall, D. (2015) 'Student Teaching and Learning Consultants: developing conversations about teaching and learning.' *Journal of Educational Innovation, Partnership and Change*, **1**(1), <https://journals.gre.ac.uk/index.php/studentchangeagents>.

Teachmint (2022). *Lecture Method of Teaching*. <https://blog.teachmint.com> Lecture Method of Teaching | A Guide (teachmint.com)

Trowler, V. (2010). *Student engagement literature review*. York: HEA https://www.heacademy.ac.uk/resources/detail/evidencenet/Student_engagement_literature_review